

Additional Data Analysis on the Effect of Gender and Background on the Risk of Email Phishing

1 Additional data analysis

Male Trainer			
Independent variable	$\alpha = 0.05$	W	p
Nationality	<i>EU</i> , NON-EU*	249	0.01037
Female Trainer			
Independent variable	$\alpha = 0.05$	W	p
Nationality	<i>EU</i> , <i>NON - EU</i>	306	0.2986

Table 1: Test of difference for participant’s perception of the trainer. The asterisk (*) marks the vector with greater values

Correctness of phishing identification									
$\alpha = 0.05; \delta = 1$		TP		TN		FP		FN	
		MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P
Gender	<i>Male - $\delta < Female$</i>	2424	0.2302	1435	1.114e-06	2002	0.0072	1299.5	7.422e-08
	<i>Female < Male + δ</i>	3914.5	7.422e-08	3212	0.0072	3779	1.114e-06	2790	0.2302
Background	UNI CS - $\delta < \text{UNI SS}$	2406	0.4162	1449	1.326e-05	1778	0.00235	1097.5	9.374e-09
	UNI SS < UNI CS + δ	3816.5	9.374e-09	3136	0.00235	3465	1.326e-05	2508	0.4162

Correctness of risk assessment									
$\alpha = 0.05; \delta = 1$		TP		TN		FP		FN	
		MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P
Gender	<i>Male - $\delta < Female$</i>	1462.5	1.428e-06	2455	0.2714	1800.5	0.0006252	991.5	1.24e-11
	<i>Female < Male + δ</i>	3757	1.237e-06	3596.5	3.673e-05	2879.5	0.1378	3748.5	9.147e-07
Background	UNI CS - $\delta < \text{UNI SS}$	1425.5	6.655e-06	2435	0.4638	1465.5	2.216e-05	1013.5	3.328e-10
	UNI SS < UNI CS + δ	3590	9.001e-07	3529.5	4.885e-06	2496.5	0.4353	3647.5	1.592e-07

Table 2: TOST of the metrics regarding phishing identification (top) and risk assessment (bottom)

Correctness of phishing identification									
Gender	n	TP		TN		FP		FN	
		μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
EU	117	5.87	1.93	1.80	1.60	6.20	1.60	2.13	1.93
NON-EU	28	5.82	2.07	2.32	2.24	5.68	2.24	2.18	2.07

Correctness of risk assessment									
Gender	n	TP		TN		FP		FN	
		μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
EU	117	5.96	1.16	2.89	2.44	6.33	2.67	0.821	1.17
NON-EU	28	5.96	1.64	3.21	2.41	5.86	2.14	0.964	1.62

Table 3: Correctness of phishing identification (top) and risk assessment (bottom). The highlighted cells mark the significant results after running the tests for difference

Correctness of phishing identification									
Nationality	$\alpha = 0.05; \delta = 1$	TP		TN		FP		FN	
		MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P
	$EU - \delta < NON - EU$	1181	0.01012	959.5	0.0002666	1278.5	0.03326	1140	0.005675
	$NON - EU < EU + \delta$	2136	0.005675	1997.5	0.03326	2316.5	0.0002666	2095	0.01012

Correctness of risk assessment									
Nationality	$\alpha = 0.05; \delta = 1$	TP		TN		FP		FN	
		MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P	MWU	P
	$EU - \delta < NON - EU$	1014.5	0.0006099	1133	0.005337	1467	0.1939	784.5	2.49e-06
	$NON - EU < EU + \delta$	2194	0.001832	1889	0.1018	2202.5	0.002204	2476	4.476e-06

Table 4: TOST of the metrics regarding phishing identification (top) and risk assessment (bottom)

Nationality	$\alpha = 0.05; \delta = 0.8$	Male Trainer		Female Trainer	
		MWU	P	MWU	P
	$EU - \delta < NON - EU$	66	1.447e-07	87	1.213e-05
	$NON - EU < EU + \delta$	542	0.06155	611	0.0003621

Table 5: TOST for participant's perception of the trainer

Male Trainer									
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
Gender (Male)	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	30	3.07	1.14	0.833	1.08	3.17	1.08	0.933	1.14
Post-training	30	3.13	1.01	0.667	0.884	3.33	0.884	0.867	1.01
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
Gender (Female)	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	70	2.48	1.01	1.18	1.15	2.82	1.15	1.52	1.01
Post-training	70	2.98	1.10	1	1.04	3	1.04	1.02	1.10
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
UNI CS	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	24	3.17	1.01	0.958	1.04	3.04	1.04	0.833	1.01
Post-training	24	3.08	1.18	0.75	0.897	3.25	0.897	0.917	1.18
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
UNI SS	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	46	2.5	1.09	1.06	1.18	2.94	1.18	1.5	1.09
Post-training	46	3.02	1	0.913	1.03	3.09	1.03	0.978	1

Female Trainer									
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
Gender (Male)	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	36	3.03	1.08	0.861	0.867	3.14	0.867	0.972	1.08
Post-training	36	3.31	1.06	1	1.15	3	1.15	0.694	1.06
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
Gender (Female)	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	39	2.77	1.06	1.03	1.16	2.97	1.16	1.23	1.06
Post-training	39	2.82	1.27	0.949	1.08	3.05	1.08	1.18	1.27
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
UNI CS	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	30	3.2	1.06	0.8	0.925	3.2	0.925	0.8	1.06
Post-training	30	3.4	0.932	0.967	1.10	3.03	1.10	0.6	0.932
		TP		TN		FP		FN	
UNI SS	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	45	2.69	1.04	1.04	1.09	2.96	1.09	1.31	1.04
Post-training	45	2.82	1.30	0.978	1.12	3.02	1.12	1.18	1.30

Table 6: The effect of trainer gender on the participant learning to correctly identify phishing emails

Male Trainer									
Gender (Male)		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	30	3	0.83	1.43	1.38	3.2	1.42	0.367	0.765
Post-training	30	3.27	0.691	1.73	1.55	2.73	1.66	0.267	0.45
Gender (Female)		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	70	2.95	0.749	1.15	1.10	3.42	1.17	0.475	0.679
Post-training	70	2.95	0.904	1.45	1.34	3.15	1.29	0.45	0.783
UNI CS		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	24	3.04	0.859	1.67	1.44	2.88	1.42	0.417	0.83
Post-training	24	3.12	0.741	1.79	1.53	2.79	1.62	0.292	0.464
UNI SS		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	46	2.94	0.742	1.06	1.06	3.56	1.15	0.435	0.655
Post-training	46	3.06	0.879	1.46	1.38	3.06	1.39	0.413	0.748

Female Trainer									
Gender (Male)		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	36	2.94	0.791	1.69	1.39	2.86	1.68	0.5	0.878
Post-training	36	2.72	0.914	1.78	1.61	3.11	1.85	0.389	0.903
Gender (Female)		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	39	3.03	0.873	1.46	1.39	2.97	1.44	0.538	0.884
Post-training	39	3.03	0.843	1.20	1.45	3.14	1.63	0.359	0.628
UNI CS		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	30	3.07	0.828	1.7	1.42	2.73	1.64	0.5	0.861
Post-training	30	2.8	0.805	1.93	1.57	2.9	1.73	0.367	0.85
UNI SS		TP		TN		FP		FN	
	n	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ	μ	σ
Pre-training	45	2.93	0.837	1.49	1.38	3.04	1.49	0.533	0.894
Post-training	45	2.93	0.939	1.18	1.47	3.51	1.71	0.378	0.716

Table 7: The effect of trainer gender on the participant learning to correctly assess the risk of phishing emails